

Excavating the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning among English Second Language Teachers in Namibia

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Abstract:

Extensive research has consistently suggested that merging research activities with teaching and learning can lead to improved effectiveness of teaching and learning. Despite the benefits of research engagement as documented in the research literature, not many teachers seem willing to engage with and in research. By exploring the English Second Language (ESL) teachers' perspectives, this study investigated the constraints and enablers of teacher research to advance the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning (SoTL) in ESL teaching practices in the Kalahari circuit in Namibia. This qualitative study collected data through focus group interviews from ESL teachers at senior secondary school levels (grades 10-12) in the Kalahari circuit, Namibia. Thematic analysis was used to analyse the data. The study found that teachers' willingness to engage in research is influenced by factors, such as school culture, research knowledge and skills, and availability of resources. It also highlights the importance of promoting the SoTL among teachers to improve teaching and learning practices. The findings of this study suggest a need for interventions, such as a training workshop, to provide targeted support and solutions to specific challenges that emerged from the research. The study recommends building communities of teacher-researchers to support and share expertise and integrate research into teaching practices, which also creates environments that value and support the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning.

Keywords: ESL Teachers, Research Publishing, SoTL, Teacher Research.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The notion of teachers as researchers has aroused academic interest (Papanastasiou & Karagiorgi, 2019). According to James and Augustin (2018), action research has consistently suggested that merging research activities with teaching and learning can lead to improved academic performance. This paper is, therefore, centred on the understanding that teacher research could play an important role in informing teaching and learning strategies. In the same vein, research indicates a renewed emphasis within educational frameworks on empowering teachers to undertake research endeavours (Papanastasiou & Karagiorgi, 2019).

Despite the benefits of research engagement as documented in the research literature, not many teachers seem to be willing to engage with and in research. Even though conducting research and publishing the outcome is an important part of the research process (Carter & Aulette, 2016), especially for the stakeholders of the practice, such as teaching, Banda (2016) shows that there is still limited teachers' involvement in conducting research and publishing their research work in academic journals.

The Namibian school curriculum was reformed by cabinet directives from the outcomes of the 2011 National Education Conference (Ministry of Education, Arts and Culture [MoEAC], 2016). The National Senior Secondary Certificate Advanced Subsidiary (NSSCAS) English as Second Language syllabus stipulates that learners at this level should be taught and guided to develop abilities that tertiary institutions highly value, including "independent learning and research" (MoEAC, 2020, p. 7). In light of this objective, it is therefore crucial that the teachers also understand and participate in research to be able to improve language instruction, guide their learners based on evidence from empirical research as well as ignite research interest in the learners. Notwithstanding little to no research or publications from the teachers at the schools, this paper acknowledges that teachers, one of the main stakeholders in education, are the closest to the data-rich field of information, which are the schools and particularly the classrooms. By exploring the English Second Language (ESL) teachers' perspectives, this study investigated the constraints and enablers of teacher research, to advance the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning (SoTL) in ESL teaching practices in the Kalahari circuit in Namibia. Specifically, the study is guided by the following research objectives and questions:

Research objectives

1. To assess English as a Second Language teachers' motivation to engage, conduct, and publish research.
2. To examine the constraints and enablers of teacher research among English as a Second Language teachers in the scholarship of teaching and learning.

Research questions

1. What factors influence English as a Second Language teachers' willingness to engage, conduct, and publish research in their teaching practice?
2. What are the constraints and enablers that impact the engagement of English as a Second Language teachers in the scholarship of teaching and learning?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical framework underpinning the study

This study is informed by the Teacher Knowledge theory. Teacher knowledge refers to the particular knowledge that teachers have that relates to knowing how to teach (Bresler, 1995). According to Bresler (1995), teacher knowledge theorists believe that research that draws on teachers' concerns and incorporates their accumulated knowledge, helps reduce the theory-practice gap, allowing authentic classroom practices to guide theory. Bresler adds that a major characteristic of teacher knowledge is that it is contextual rather than abstract. In their project *Teacher Assessment Knowledge and Practice: A Narrative Inquiry of a Chinese College EFL Teacher's Experience*, Xu and Liu (2015) warn that teacher knowledge is not something objective and independent of the teacher. It is a collection of the teacher's whole personal, social, academic, and professional experience.

Therefore, this study reveres the pluralistic nature of teachers' experiences. Additionally, it also presupposes that their active participation in research and resulting findings can richly inform effective ESL teaching and learning. The study is also anchored in the notion of Scholarship of Teaching and Learning as its theoretical underpinning. The term 'Scholarship of teaching and learning,' (henceforth SoTL) was popularised in the 1990s by Ernest Boyer, a teaching scholar who advocated for sustained teaching and learning approaches and outcomes (Boyer, 1990; Stierer, 2008).

Accordingly, in the teaching and learning context, classrooms are sources of questions about teaching and learning to inform the design of instruction, and share their discoveries with their colleagues. It is important to note that there were some doubts regarding the SoTL and the excellence of scholarly work. Thus, research was conducted on this issue, and the findings generated six standards of excellence in scholarship. That is, published work must have clear goals, be systematic with appropriate methods, achieve outstanding results, communicate effectively, and the scholars reflectively critique their work (Glassick¹, 2010).

Although SoTL was initially more focused on higher education, there are several applications of this approach in basic education, where teachers are also encouraged to conduct scholarly inquiries on teaching and learning in their contexts, to improve teaching and learning practices. It is for this reason that this study also embraces other

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perspectives on the promotion of scholarly inquiry among teachers, which are, in this regard, in congruence with SoTL. One of them is teacher research, which is viewed as action research (Stremmel, 2002). Teacher research reverberates the stance of this study, considering that teacher research aims to bring change and improvement to a problematic situation.

In this study, it is understood that both teacher research and action research are perspectives that contribute to the promotion of SoTL among teachers. That is, both research approaches can be applied to help teachers become teacher researchers and proponents of SoTL. According to Fanghanel (2013), SoTL can be viewed as a modern methodology for professional development that aligns teaching and research activities to advance the development of an approach to scholarly inquiry. It is, therefore, based on this understanding that this study is aimed at investigating the teachers' readiness for SoTL in the Namibian context.

Lastly, this study also reveres Archer's (1995, 2000) Morphogenetic Theory, which specifically informed the study's data analysis through the lenses of structure, culture, and agency (SCA). Based on Archer's lenses of SCA, in the context of this study, structure refers to the social and institutional arrangements that may constrain and/or enable teachers to conduct and publish research, and advance SoTL. Culture refers to the society or community's ideational attributes, such as beliefs (cultural, political, or religious), values, and norms that may also constrain and/or enable teachers to conduct and publish research, and advance SoTL. Agency relates to the ESL teachers' willingness and capacity regarding their involvement in research and publication. This may be influenced by the teachers' willingness, values, ability, and support to contribute to research and publication.

2.2 Strategies for teacher preparation for SoTL

Available literature presents various avenues for cultivating teachers' readiness for the SoTL. First, the European Commission (2023) recommends that to facilitate the transformation of teachers towards research-oriented teachers, practice-oriented research should be part of the school leaders' and teachers' professional development programmes. The Commission also stressed that there is a need for quality teacher education that promotes research knowledge, skills, and attitude. The need for this intervention earlier in the teacher training program appears to be recognised in the Namibian context. For instance, in the Bachelor of Education (Secondary) (Honours) program at the University of Namibia, student teachers are required to take a research module designed to enhance their theoretical and practical research knowledge and skills. First, the students complete a third-year module 'Educational Research' which "focuses on issues of theory and methodology in educational research... [It also assists the students through the process of writing their] research proposal, [and] designing data collection instruments" (UNAM, 2023, p. 219). Second, the students take a fourth-year module "Educational Research Project" where they are required to collect data, analyse it

and complete a research report (UNAM, 2023). Research may be needed to assess and confirm the effectiveness of these arrangements, and whether the introduction to research in the last two years of the programmes is sufficient to prepare the teachers for the teaching practices that embrace SoTL.

It is also recommended that, for teachers to be inclined to engage in research, policies at the school level should also be favourable towards a culture of research, reflective practice, and inquiry-based teaching and learning (European Commission, 2023). Schools can avail or allocate time exclusively for discussing and using research. For example, a school may schedule meetings that are specifically aimed at research use and applying a research-informed approach to addressing certain issues in the school (European Commission, 2023). This may help teachers become professional in reading and researching to improve their practice. This can further be enhanced when teachers are not only encouraged to read research undertaken by experts. Instead, according to Papanastasiou and Karagiorgi (2019), teacher educators should equip teachers to develop knowledge and skills for them to become actively involved in research to improve their instruction.

Apart from teacher training programmes, professional development programmes can also be avenues for transforming teachers into teacher researchers who embrace SoTL in their teaching practices. For example, training workshops can be organised through the UNAM's (2024a) Continuing Professional Development Unit, which coordinates continuing professional development programmes for all UNAM academics, and other educators and professionals. The unit aims at improving the quality of learning in the general education sector and at UNAM. The unit's targeted beneficiaries are therefore general education educators such as school teachers, school managers, and education officers, as well as higher education educators such as lecturers at UNAM. In the same regard, reference can be made to Monash University (2023), which has developed, through 'The Monash Q Project', a professional learning short course called 'An Introduction to Using Research to Inform Educational Practice'. The course guides participants in how to access research, appraise it for rigour and relevance, and implement it thoughtfully. The course instructional strategy consists of self-paced learning modules, videos, resources, and activities, including practical case studies from Australian teachers.

All in all, so far, it is understood in this paper that research is about generating new understanding and solving the actual problems in given areas (Erba, 2013). This paper further incites Haxhihyseni and Muho's (2015) view that research is the most appropriate method to explore ways to improve one's teaching practices and improve quality learning outcomes for learners. The issue of teaching without research is a concern in this paper, especially since research tends to be highly mystified and believed to be for the few in higher institutions of learning, such as universities (Banda, 2016).

3. METHODS

This study is situated on the interpretivism philosophical worldview, a perspective that aims to incorporate depth into the gained insight (Alharahsheh & Pius, 2020). The participants, ESL teachers, involved in the study, provided their insight into the phenomenon of reality as a product of subjective experience. The study employs a qualitative approach, which tends to be inductive to meaning creation (Leavy, 2014), to carefully study, examine, and learn about the constraints and enablers of teacher research for publication.

The target population was the ESL teachers at senior secondary school levels (grades 10-12) in the ||Kharas region, Namibia. There are three circuits in the region with a total of sixteen (16) secondary schools. Purposive sampling was used to select one circuit, the Kalahari circuit, which consists of six (6) secondary schools. That is, the sample of the study was 30 ESL teachers in the Kalahari circuit out of 85 ESL teachers in the ||IKharas region. The primary criterion for the selection of this circuit was that it has more senior secondary schools compared to the other circuits. Also, considering that the region is sparsely populated, the secondary schools in the Kalahari circuit were in proximity to the main town of Keetmanshoop.

Data were collected through focus group interviews with the selected ESL teachers, where they engaged in a discussion with the researchers. The main focus was on establishing the teachers' perspective on research and publishing to establish the constraints and enablers to advancing SOTL in ESL teaching practices. The discussions took place on the school premises (of each selected school) after school in venues that were agreed upon with the participants. The discussion lasted for about 60 minutes. With consent from the teachers, the discussions were audio-recorded to enable accurate analysis of the data.

Thematic analysis was employed to analyse data through the lenses of SCA as emphasised in Archer's (1995, 2003) Morphogenetic Theory. The study also followed Taylor-Powell and Renner's (2003) steps for narrative data analysis. After the recordings were transcribed, the first step involved thoroughly reading (three times) the transcribed texts (participants' responses) and coding the data. Second, the analysis identified consistencies and differences in the responses and then categorised them under different themes or patterns. The final analysis categorised the constraints and enablers of SoTL among ESL teachers under the lens of SCA. The presentation of the findings also followed the thematic approach while reference to the data (interview strands) used pseudonyms to maintain the participants' anonymity and confidentiality.

The Ethical Clearance Certificate was obtained from the University of Namibia Expedited Research Ethics Committee.

4. FINDINGS

This study reveals significant insights into the factors influencing ESL teachers' involvement in research and publishing activities. It highlights key constraints and enablers that inform the understanding of the current state of teacher research within the ESL community, and also inform the potential for SoTL in ELS teaching practices. Lastly, the study analyses the constraints through the morphogenetic theory's lenses of SCA, which, according to Archer (1995, 2003), enables a comprehensive understanding of the contextual status of SoTL among ELS teachers in the region under study.

4.1 Teachers' understanding of research and publication

Regarding the ESL teachers' understanding of what research entails, the study found that some of the teachers relate research to the process of investigating issues in a given setting. One of the teachers indicated that, *"It's maybe when one notices and you want to find more about it or to evaluate and yeah, OK"* (P11). Interestingly, it is also understood that research and publishing should be followed by action or implementation, considering one teacher's response that: *"I don't see the need of doing research and then it's all only on paper. And nothing is done after that. So, it needs to be also implemented"* P4. Including the element of practical implementation to research and not limiting it to theory is supported by Stremmel (2002), who emphasises that this type of inquiry fosters improvement in educational practices.

The teachers also appear to view research as ongoing since new issues for investigation continue to surface. They responded that:

Research for publication is ongoing because every research has some sort of gap. So, whoever reads research A can conduct research B based on the gap of A. P3
"Other researchers who have already done in most cases you will find one or two sources where you can get information that you can already build on. (P4)

It is thus understood that research and publication enable research to build on the research gaps arising from previous research, enabling continued scholarly inquiry. This view resonates with the principle of action research as a cyclical process where "a complete cycle of research (i.e., one actual research study) builds on and extends any cycles of action research into the same or closely related problem that preceded it (Mertler, 2012, p. 4).

The data suggest the need for all stakeholders of language education to participate in research and publication. One teacher indicated that, *"I think everyone involved in language teaching should come on board because any research won't help if it is just for a few people"* (P6). This suggests that engagement in research activities serves as a crucial form of professional development for teachers. The data further suggested that

conducting literature reviews, for example, is a useful skill in teaching. For example, one teacher indicated that, *“With the literature review, and then because I’m also teaching geography, it’s a topic we have to teach the learners on how to conduct research”* (P24). The literature suggests that a non-collaborative culture in schools can act as a barrier to research engagement (Barkhuizen, 2009). Understandably, this engagement can improve not only research participation rates but also enhance the quality of teaching through community support and shared learning experiences.

It was interesting to observe that some teachers appreciate research publications. For instance, one participant remarked, *“You publish it [research] for those interested and those involved to see if it can work or to implement it”* (P5). This is to say, publishing research enables one not only to solve problems but also to share solutions and discoveries, in this case, with the ELS teaching community. It also serves as a source of information that provides an unbiased, holistic view of teaching since, according to one of the teacher participants, *“The more you read interpretations from different writers and people, you get different views and opinions. So, you understand and see whether a problem can be solved or minimised or tackled from a different perspective”* (P3).

Some of the teachers seem to understand the role of data in establishing truth through research. It appears to be understood that research is not a mere search for solutions by intuition or personal experience. One teacher participant explained that:

[Research is about] identifying the solution to the existing problem and also to fill the gap that you think exists in a certain area. But by filling that gap as an academic, you don’t just impose your ideas. So, you have to gather data from other people or other sources to conclude that this can be the solution to a problem that has existed or that exists. (P7)

Some teachers appreciate research in terms of the opportunity it presents for improving one’s multidisciplinary knowledge. One of the teachers explained that:

As I’m doing research now, I found something interesting, something that I didn’t know, for instance. I’m thinking when I did my research, I never knew that a baby below the weight of 2.5 kilograms, even if it’s a full-term birth, is regarded as premature. (P10)

Therefore, teachers understand that research not only improves their knowledge in their field but they also come across useful information from other disciplines, equipping them with multidisciplinary knowledge and awareness. The role of teachers’ multidisciplinary knowledge and awareness has been commended in the literature. Adeyemi (2010)

emphasised that the global world is a culturally and linguistically diverse entity that can best be understood in an integrated way; hence, multidisciplinary-based instruction enables learners to engage contrasting perspectives and critically synthesise, think, and re-examine the world taken for granted.

Research is also viewed as a tool for transformation and change of the status quo. For example, one teacher indicated that *“The problems that our parents had are not as what kids nowadays are having. So, we can’t use those solutions with these kids as well”* (P20). This suggests that teachers perceive research as an instrument for shaping ESL teaching to suit the current needs of the learners, which may be slightly different from the teaching and learning context of the past. However, some of the teacher participants still did not see the need for research and publication other than when they did it to fill the requirements for a qualification. For example, one of them remarked that, *“Yeah. OK. For my paper, Yeah. My qualification, Yeah. But for publishing, what do I get from there?”* (P12).

So far, the data suggest that the teachers have a relatively good awareness of research and view it as an essential resource for assessing and enhancing their teaching methods. Notably, they indicated that research ought to produce results that can be put into practice, which is in line with Gaffney’s (2008) finding that research can help identify issues and bring about change in the classroom. Furthermore, the teachers seem to view educational inquiry as a continuous process. This finding is in keeping with the iterative cycles of reflective practice proposed by Noffke (2009) that the understanding of expanding on existing research represents an aspiration toward scholarly growth and the ongoing improvement of teaching methodologies.

4.2 Teachers’ self-assessment of research competencies and the need for support

The teachers’ self-assessment of their research competencies reveals that, to some extent, they possess some level of proficiency in some research areas. These areas include conducting literature reviews, research publishing, research report structure, and coherence (see Table 1 below).

Table 1
Teachers' competencies in some research areas

Research component	Participants' responses
Conducting literature reviews	<p>"I go for literature review because I enjoy reading and now putting those things together because even the solution is where you are putting those things and you are analysing them". (P7)</p> <p>"My strongest point or section in research is the literature review". (P18)</p>
Research publishing	<p>"So, you don't just identify the problem and solve it, and then you keep it to yourself. Yeah, yeah". (P9)</p> <p>"I have seen that there are also sites where you can upload your document and for the audience to read your resource". (P2)</p> <p>"It's also very important to publish so that it should be known it should be not only to a particular place but worldwide, globally, nationally, and so forth". (P10)</p>
Research report structure and coherence	<p>"I always make sure that there is structure; it flows. You see, the one thing". (P8)</p>

In line with the agenda of promoting SoTL in teaching practices, the teachers' responses in Table 1 above suggest the teachers' understanding and appreciation of the dissemination of research findings in the public domain. While noting that other research competencies are needed to conduct research and publish it, this study acknowledges that the already-existing competencies among the teachers are an advantage to the realisation of the agenda of promoting SoTL in ESL teaching practices.

It is, however, worth noting that the teachers also indicated that they may need support in the form of training and, in some cases, on how such an intervention should be implemented. One teacher affirmed that "*Why not? Because it's a learning process for yourself. So, I will also definitely be interested in training*" (P4). The teachers' interest in research training is further confirmed by their acknowledgement of the lack of skills in some research components. For example, one teacher specifically shared that, "*I enjoyed the literature review because of the love for reading, but the others were really poor*" (P6). Teachers may need structured support systems such as formalised mentorship programs and training workshops on research methodologies. In this regard, one teacher stated that, "*Even during my studies, I had no classes, so I just taught myself. Everything was just through the phone or email. You check the comments and realise that 'I even have to restart'*" (P8). This suggests a need for adequate guidance to improve the teachers' research skills and publishing skills because, without such guidance, their progress may be hampered. Other competence gaps include uncertainty about the research process as

well as limited confidence in one's research focus or work. One teacher revealed that, *"I question myself. Why am I doing this research if three or four people already tried and it's not working well?"* (P3).

The teachers' responses propose that there is a need for a detailed and practical intervention to effectively improve the teachers' research skills. One teacher pointed out *"If you just comment on 'what is this', 'you do this this', without actually giving a practical thing, then I will not understand after that. Give me an example of like, but then also like go in detail"* (P10). Other teachers equally shared that they may need detailed training that is *"starting from scratch"* P5, *addressing specific components such as "data analysis"* (P8) and focusing on *"How to come up with the research topic, research questions, research objectives, methods and so on"* (P2). Moreover, there was also an interest in a mentorship programme where, for example, teachers can be connected to research experts who then serve as their research mentors. One teacher responded that *"Having a mentor is very interesting, actually necessary. Yeah, it does help you with your professional and academic growth"* (P8).

It is, therefore, understood here that there is a need for interventions that include hands-on activities and use real-world examples to enable comprehension of abstract concepts. For example, regarding the difficulty in formulating a research problem, the intervention should not just be a mere presentation that follows traditional lecture methods, but the teachers need to have a practical, detailed walk-through of the process of formulating. Accordingly, the European Commission (2023) supports teachers' transition to become research-oriented educators and directs them toward practice-oriented professional development opportunities. The results also highlight the significance of supportive school environments.

4.3 Teachers' awareness of researchable areas in the fields of practice

The results show that the teachers have some awareness of researchable areas in their field. These areas are presented along with the teachers' responses in Table 2 below:

Table 2

Teacher awareness of researchable areas in their fields or practices

Research area	Participant's response
writing interest and learner motivation	"Maybe we can provide ways that can make the learners to kind of give them an interest in writing longer or shorter pieces of writing". (P3)
curriculum articulation	"I think there is also that gap: I feel like they [students] have not mastered certain competencies coming from grade 7 to grade 8". (P16) "We can research why the learners when they get to grade 8, still cannot write properly even with the use of a dictionary". (P23)
diagnostic assessment	"Bringing the kids over to high school from primary school, I think there's a need for something to test their competence, especially with English". (P17)
leadership and management	"I have an interest in leadership and management. So, how can the teacher take the role of a motivating leader, somebody that the learners can look up to?" (P2)
inclusivity and addressing learning difficulties	"I am interested in how I, as a language teacher, am going to identify the learner with a problem and then secondly, find the means to assist that learner. How am I going to include that child in my mainstream". (P6)

The teachers' awareness of researchable areas represents an essential first step towards improving professional practices, allowing teachers to use empirical data to guide their lesson plans and improve learner outcomes, which indicates a desire to engage in reflective practices. Such scholarly research is essential, especially since study findings have maintained that it yields better curriculum designs and instructional improvements that are responsive to the needs of learners (Singh & Gelat, 2022). The identification of researchable areas points to a possible alignment with the larger goals of the SoTL.

Considering that the teachers have an awareness of some researchable areas in their practices, it is promising, to some extent, that there is a potential for the teachers to advance the SoTL in their practices. Hence, if teachers are equipped with the necessary research methodology skills, they can be in a better position to scientifically investigate learning issues, such as the ones shared above.

4.4 Teachers' barriers to conducting research in the teaching practice

The analysis shows that there are some constraining factors for teachers to conduct research and publish within their teaching practice. One of them is the difficulty of having access to research participants due to the participants' willingness to be part of research

studies. One of the teachers, interestingly, confessed that, initially, they were also not willing to take part in this (the current) study, stating that, “*Finding research participants is a challenge. To be honest with you, I was also not interested in being part of this discussion*” (P16). According to DePoy and Gitlin (2016), reluctance to participate in research tends to be attributed to the target participants’ concern about the confidentiality of their data, beneficence, and ignorance about certain concepts and procedures. However, they add that refusal may also be an indicator of the significance of the topic under study, which should be considered worth investigating.

It should be noted, though, that sometimes one may have access to the participants, yet access to data from the participants can also be a challenge. This is to say, while one may refuse to participate, others may agree to participate yet be reluctant to respond to the questions or fully engage in the discussions. For example, the teachers were concerned with the possibility of getting inaccurate information from the participants due to certain cultural factors. All in all, there is a need for awareness of the role of research in teaching and learning, not only among teachers but all education stakeholders who may in some way be eligible for inclusion in the target population of a given educational research study.

Another challenge is the limited access to research materials. While the teachers noted the availability of a Teacher Resource Centre (TRC) in their area (in the Kalahari circuit), they indicated that, “*TRC has useful teaching materials, but not more on research*” (P3). Therefore, despite the teachers’ willingness to advance the SoTL, the limited research resources create an uncondusive environment for research and publishing, leaving them with limited competencies in certain research methodologies and an inability to explore various issues that may require investigation under certain research approaches (e.g. qualitative, quantitative, or mixed-method). For example, one teacher shared that, “*I always go for qualitative where I have to do my case studies with*” (P7). However, preference for one research approach may limit the teachers to explore certain issues since each research type has a different purpose and approach that helps in solving its question (Bhoshale, 2023). Technological skills were also reported as some of the challenges, where one teacher indicated that, “*I’m technologically challenged*” (P8).

The study further found that some teachers were not willing to conduct and publish research in their teaching practice since it had no tangible reward. One teacher responded that, “*I’m to do the research, only if I’m to be rewarded*”. (P14). They also indicated that they found it difficult to conduct research for publication due to heavy workloads. One teacher indicated that, “*One of the challenges would be time. When will I do that if my timetable is full*” (P8). Other teachers also confirmed similar concerns, citing the added personal responsibilities of being an adult. They shared that:

It will take a lot of time, honestly speaking. If you have a house and kids and so on, later it becomes complicated.
(P1)

Yes, so being a triangular citizen, you are a teacher, you are a parent, and you also have other things to live up to.
(P2)

There were also concerns with publication fees, possibly because the teachers would not be inclined to pay for research publications that do not bring immediate, tangible rewards. One teacher indicated that, “*We have to pay certain fees. If it was free then is a motivation*” (P7). This finding suggests that the burden of publication fees is a significant economic deterrent that stresses cost as a barrier to active teacher research. The results reveal several obstacles preventing research initiatives from being carried out effectively. A similar study by Noffke (2009) also noted obstacles like high workload, non-collaborative school cultures, and the absence of easily accessible resources and research infrastructures for educators who are eager to conduct research in their field.

4.5 Teachers’ motivation to conduct research for publication

One of the key motivating factors for teachers to conduct research is their research skills. The teachers acknowledge that they had acquired some research skills, especially from different educational programmes they attended. One teacher reported that “*I did a research module when I was doing my Master’s in Education in Curriculum Studies*” (P3). Another teacher shared that “*At the college, we got training on how to do research*” (P10). Another key motivating factor is the availability of research materials, especially online resources. The teachers acknowledged that access to the Internet is the main enabler for access to a wide range of research sources and materials. One teacher indicated that “*It’s only online materials available. There are some journals in print, but very very few*” (P14). Another teacher shared that “*I would say at school we have the Internet*” (P3). It is worth pointing out that the teacher’s response above acknowledged the availability of advanced technology, the cell phone, a tool with information-accessing abilities that was not available some decades ago. According to Husnita et al. (2023), the ability to access learning materials and educational resources via mobile devices has opened the door to distance learning and self-study.

The teachers could also access useful research material from institutions of higher learning, such as the University of Namibia’s institutional repository (recently renamed “UNAM Gā-aisib² Repository”) (UNAM, 2024b). One of the teachers indicated that “*Through institutions like UNAM, you can go through. You know they have a repository where you can go and go through other people’s research so that you can either learn about the methodology that they have used*” (P8). In the same vein, another teacher added that:

² Gā-aisib is a term from a Namibian language, Khoekhoegowab, meaning “wisdom” (UNAM, 2024b, para. 2).

That is a resource on its own. So, institutions, are different, they are a lot, like UNAM and IUM [The International University of Management] and many others. So through their engine. We can get our resources. Yeah, and they are free of charge. It can help you with your literature review and you can learn from other studies how to analyse the results and so on. (P9)

Apart from the repositories, the teachers specified some of the resources that they could access on the Internet, such as e-books, where one can learn different research methodologies. They, however, indicated that one may need certain internet search or navigation skills to work with some online platforms. In this regard, the teachers indicated that:

Of course, ebooks, where you can access a whole lot of resources. P24

You can learn the research methodology from those of those guys. So you can learn from them, as long as you know how to search because they say there is a certain method of searching information. (P6)

Another notable motivating factor is that some of the teachers' interest and willingness to advance SoTL were inspired by people around them, such as their family members. One teacher shared that "*I am familiar with some journals. Not so much, but I have a family member who is so much into academics, and I've seen that she publishes in some journals. So, I was inspired*" (P17). The inspiration to publish research in academic journals was also indicated by other teachers. For example, one teacher indicated that:

Why put so much effort into something that you don't want others to see? I want to publish it because I want people to see it. The people in education and our future leaders can benefit from my work. That is what makes me excited and motivated to get whatever I research to be published. (P9)

Lastly, the analysis suggests that the teachers' motivation to engage in research activities would be improved if there were support from the school supervisors as well to facilitate research engagements. One teacher suggested that, "*We need support from school management or regional offices. They need to allow you to do research. Otherwise, the school hours are currently only for lesson*" (P13).

Despite the challenges expressed by the participants, the results revealed several motivators that can foster research engagement among teachers. The teachers' acknowledgement of the benefits of receiving research training and the accessibility of online resources point to a future direction for improving their research competencies. This echoes Leuverink and Aarts' (2021) sentiments that teachers who participated in the teacher-research initiative tended to be more motivated to incorporate new concepts and ongoing evaluation into their teaching practices. Peer encouragement also seemed to motivate some teachers to consider publishing their research. This implies that raising engagement levels can be achieved by fostering an environment of inquiry where successes are acknowledged. School administrators can create cultures that value and honour research contributions to recognise or reward those who successfully integrate teaching and research.

4.6 Constraints and enablers of the SoTL among ESL teachers through the lenses of structure, culture, and agency

Overall, this study has found that there are existing enablers and constraints to integrating SoTL among ESL teachers. Through Archer's morphogenetic lenses of structure, culture and agencies, further analysis can enable a better contextualisation of the case of ESL teachers in the ||Kharas region regarding the SoTL. In Table 3 below, the study presents the analysis of the constraints and enablers through the lens of SCA. Based on Archer's morphogenetic theory and the lenses of SCA, this analysis allows for a refined comprehension of the relationship of social forces and ESL teachers' agency in the practice of SoTL (Archer, 1995, 2003). In this way, the analysis enables more comprehensive insights that facilitate problem-solving and targeted interventions to advance SoTL among ESL teachers. Table 3 below presents the findings on the constraints and enablers of the SoTL among ESL teachers through the lenses of structure, culture, and agency.

Table 3
Constraints and enablers of the SoTL among ESL teachers through the lenses of structure, culture, and agency

Lense	Constraint	Enabler
Structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of research training (methodologies, writing) • Limited Institutional Support for SoTL (school/MEAC) • Limited Access to Research Materials (limited research materials in local TRCs) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal support systems (e.g. mentorship, training workshops) • Research Skills from Educational Programs (previously acquired research skills) • Supportive school environments (sharing research experiences and encouraging research engagement)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time Constraints Due to Workload (professional and personal responsibilities) • Publication Fees (reluctancy to pay publication fees) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to Online Resources (UNAM's repository)
Culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-Collaborative School Culture (limiting opportunities for shared learning and research engagement) • Perception of Research as Requirement-Driven (to fulfil qualification requirements rather than for professional growth) • Lack of Participant Willingness (Cultural pride and concerns about confidentiality) • Perception of Research as Non-Incentivised (Research is not valued or rewarded sufficiently) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appreciation for Research and Publication (improving teaching practices, gaining multidisciplinary knowledge, and transforming the status quo) • Perception of Research as Ongoing (new gaps to explore can motivate ongoing research engagement) • Peer and Family Influence (Inspiration in the community or network)
Agency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited Confidence and Uncertainty (research focus and in their work, respectively) • Perceived Lack of Immediate Benefits (no tangible benefit other than qualification) • Limited technological and digital skills (digital research writing and data analysis tools) • Lack of Research Methodology Skills (e.g. reliance on qualitative methods due to a lack of confidence or skills in other methodologies. • Professional Development (drive to advance one's professional skills) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competencies in Research Components (literature reviews, report structuring, and publishing) • Awareness of Research Impact (actionable changes) • Intrinsic motivation (Eagerness to solve problems in ESL teaching and learning)

In the final analysis, this study has established that there is an interplay between structural (institutional support, training programs), cultural (shared beliefs and values around research), and agential (individual teachers' motivations and competencies) factors in shaping the SoTL among ELS teachers.

5. CONCLUSION

By exploring the ESL teachers' perspectives, this study investigated the constraints and enablers of teacher research to advance the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning in ESL teaching practices. The study found that although ESL teachers acknowledge the value of research in enhancing teaching strategies, numerous obstacles impede their ability to conduct and publish research. These barriers include limited access to resources, a lack of support, and heavy workloads that leave little time for research. The teachers demonstrate a fundamental understanding of a range of researchable topics and a desire to use research to enhance their practices despite these obstacles.

The findings suggest that there is a potential for professional growth among teachers if supportive structures, such as professional development programs, mentorship opportunities, and collaborative inquiry environments, are established. Access to research materials can be made easier by using contemporary technology and internet resources. Teachers can be encouraged to participate in research more actively through various professional development programs focusing on research. The findings highlight the need for focused interventions that remove identified barriers and promote an inquiry-based culture to advance the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning (SoTL) among ESL teachers. To improve the quality of education for both teachers and learners, education stakeholders ought to prioritise research as a crucial component of instructional practice. This will foster an environment that supports teacher research in Namibia.

The study recommends establishing professional development programs through frequent workshops on research. This can be done in collaboration with the Advisory Services under the Directorate of Education. This will enable teachers to close skill gaps, collaborate more effectively, and be provided with support. The study further recommends that schools work with nearby libraries or universities to provide access to academic journals and textbooks to improve the availability of research materials for teachers. Teachers are also encouraged to use digital tools and platforms that provide databases, e-books, and online training materials.

Moreover, the study recommends creating a system of incentives for teachers who conduct and publish research, rewards, professional recognition, and career advancement opportunities. Moreover, platforms for showcasing and appreciating teachers for their research contributions ought to be established. To improve collaborative education research, the study recommends creating interdisciplinary research programs that bring together educators from different fields to address common

educational issues. Collaborations between schools and universities can be encouraged to give ESL teachers more access to materials, professional development, and opportunities for mentorship from experienced researchers.

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Declaration of conflict of interest

We hereby declare that we, and our funder, have no financial, professional, or personal conflicts of interest that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this research article.

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